

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR R₂TIX

R	X	m.p. °C	Analytical data, found (calcd) % element				IR absorption bands				
			TI	C	H	N	ν_3	ν_1	ν_2	ν_4	Combina- tion band
phenyl	NO ₃	>320	48.7 (48.6)	34.6 (34.3)	2.5 (2.4)	3.2 (3.3)	1380 vs	1042 m	808 w	b	1750 w
<i>o</i> -tolyl	„	308-10d	46.0 (45.5)	37.9 (37.5)	2.9 (3.1)	3.2 (3.1)	1380 vs	1038 s	812 w	705 w	1745 w
<i>m</i> -tolyl ^a	„	318 d	45.9	37.3	3.2	3.3	1380 vs	1040 w	805 w	710 m	1750 w
<i>p</i> -tolyl ^a	„	>320	46.0	38.0	3.3	3.2	1370 vs	1038 m	815 w	715 m	1755 w
phenyl	NO ₂	>320	50.5 (50.5)	36.0 (35.6)	2.5 (2.3)	3.5 (3.5)	1208 vs	1325 sh	833 m	—	2490 w
<i>o</i> -tolyl	„	297-99d	47.5 (47.2)	39.5 (38.8)	2.9 (3.2)	3.3 (3.2)	1210 s	1325 vs	840 w	—	—
<i>m</i> -tolyl ^a	„	262 d	47.6	38.9	3.4	3.4	1200 vs	1335 vs	830 m	—	2520 w
<i>p</i> -tolyl ^a	„	292 d	47.4	39.1	3.3	3.3	1210 vs	1335 s	835 m	—	2480 w

a=calculated data for *m* and *p* tolyl derivatives are the same as for *o*-tolyl

b=masked by C-H out of plane deformation

d=decomposes

s=strong, m=medium, sh=shoulder, v=very, w=weak

The compounds are white solids, insoluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, diethyl ether etc., but dissolve appreciably in pyridine, dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. They decompose around 300° before melting. Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solution in dimethyl formamide at 35° is found to be in the range 58.2 - 80.6 ohm⁻¹ cm² moles⁻¹, indicating 1 : 1 electrolytic character of the compounds.

The infrared spectra of the compounds in nujol were recorded in the region 4000 - 400 cm⁻¹ using Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model 337. The absorptions associated with the aromatic group are observed at position reported by us in one of our earlier publications⁷, are not listed here. The absorptions associated with various modes of vibration of the nitrate and nitrite groups are summarised in the last column of the Table.

In the spectra of diarylthallium (III) nitrates, four absorptions located at 1375 ± 5, 1040 ± 2, 810 ± 5, and 710 ± 5 cm⁻¹ are assigned to asym stretching ν_3 , sym stretching ν_1 , bending ν_2 and planar rocking ν_4 modes of vibration of the nitrate group respectively. The values are in the range reported for ionic nitrates⁸, and thus strongly support our conductance data suggesting the compounds to be 1 : 1 electrolytes. An absorption of weak intensity occurring in the spectra of all diarylthallium (III) nitrates at 1750 ± 5 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to a combination band denoted by $\nu_1 + \nu_4$.

In the spectra of the four newly synthesised diarylthallium(III) nitrites three anionic absorptions namely ν_1 and ν_3 associated with the stretching modes of the NO₂ group and ν_2 , the bending mode, appear at 1330 ± 5, 1205 ± 5 and 835 ± 5 cm⁻¹ respectively. The results suggest ionic character of the nitrites in view of the reported data of Sidman⁹ on sodium nitrite and support our high conductance values in dimethylformamide solution. Besides the three fundamental modes of absorption, a weak combination or overtone at 2500 ± 20 cm⁻¹ is also observed which may be either $\nu_1 + \nu_3$ or $2\nu_3$.

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Preparation and Characterisation of Double Acetates of Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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ANHYDROUS acetates of nickel (II) and cobalt (II) are insoluble in acetic anhydride but they readily form clear solutions when alkali metal and thallos and ammonium acetates are added to their solutions. Nothing separates out when these solutions are either chilled or some inert solvent is added. However yellow (nickel) and violet (cobalt) compounds separate out when ether is added to these solutions.

They are all sticky mass and do not dry up even on keeping them under vacuum for 72 hours. Elemental analysis corresponds to the composition $M_2 [Ni(OAc)_4] \cdot 24H_2O$ and $M_2 [Co(OAc)_4] \cdot 24H_2O$ where M stands for monovalent metal. But when these compounds are heated to about 50°C under reduced pressure compounds of composition $M_2 [Ni(OAc)_4] \cdot xAc_2O$ and $M_2 [Co(OAc)_4] \cdot xAc_2O$, where x may have a value of 4 or 6, are left behind. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been determined by elemental analysis and are reported in Table I. It is interesting to note that the number of acetic anhydride molecules attached with the compounds vary with the alkali metal used. In the case of lithium, it is maximum i. e. six and in the case of cesium and thallous the number of the solvent molecules is four only which may be due to high polarizability of lithium due to its smaller size.

All these compounds are extremely hygroscopic and decompose before melting. They are soluble in acetonitrile, dioxane and dimethylformamide. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions in acetonitrile suggest their ionic nature. When molecular weights are determined in dimethylformamide, complicated results are obtained, possibly ligand displacement reactions take place and it is not possible to characterise the intermediate products at this stage.

All these compounds are paramagnetic in nature as is evident from Table 1. As the colour of these compound is not a good evidence for their stereochemistry a careful study of their stereochemistry is in progress. Magnetic moment values of all these compounds have been determined at room temperature. In the case of cobalt compounds, for an octahedral

field, the ground state ($4T_1$) is orbitally degenerate and causes an orbital angular momentum contribution to the magnetic moment and the moment lies between 3.88 and 5.2 BM¹. The experimental values depend upon the amount of total orbital angular momentum associated with the ground state orbital triplet. The experimental values in the present studies we close to this range and an octahedral environment around cobalt may be proposed. Similarly, the observed magnetic values for the nickel (II) compounds are very close to the values for nickel (II) in an octahedral environment which has $3A_{2g}$ as the ground state². A slightly higher values of the magnetic moment than the reported values may be due to orbital contribution or slight distortion in the octahedral symmetry round the central atom.

Thermogravimetric analysis of these double acetates show the same general trend of decomposition. From the percentage loss of weight, calculated from the thermograms, it is observed that in the case of lithium and sodium double acetates, four molecules of acetic anhydride are lost at $\sim 150^\circ$ while at 220°C the remaining two acetic anhydride molecules are lost. In the case of other acetates, two solvent molecules are lost at $\sim 130^\circ$ and the remaining solvent molecules are lost at 180°. At $\sim 370^\circ$ there is again loss due to alkali metal acetates. At $\sim 500^\circ$, the cobalt (II) and nickel (II) acetates decompose to the corresponding oxides which have been identified from the weight of the residue and elemental analysis. Trend of decomposition of these acetates is quite similar to that of oxalates which form oxides rather than carbonates³. Higher dissociation temperatures of lithium and sodium double acetates may be attributed to ion-dipole interaction.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF DOUBLE ACETATES OF COBALT (II) AND NICKEL (II)

Compound	Colour & Physical State	m.p. (°C)	Molecular Weight		%Transition Metal		Molar conductance in Acetonitrile (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Magnetic Moment BM
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.		
Li ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]6Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	96°D	901	921	6.3	6.4	205.5	4.83
Na ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]6Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	85°D	980	953	6.04	6.19	150.6	4.85
K ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]4Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	65°D	762	781	7.43	7.55	250.8	4.87
Cs ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]2Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	84°D	792	765	7.80	7.71	225.0	4.78
(NH ₄) ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]4Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	78°D	719	739	7.86	7.98	190.4	4.84
Tl ₂ [Co(OAc) ₄]2Ac ₂ O	Pinkish violet solid	80°D	927	907.7	6.54	6.49	180.6	4.80
Li ₂ [Ni(OAc) ₄]6Ac ₂ O	Yellow solid	98°D	908	920.7	6.30	6.37	182.5	3.42
Na ₂ [Ni(OAc) ₄]6Ac ₂ O	Yellow solid	76°D	934	952.7	6.28	6.16	232.2	3.38
K ₂ [Ni(OAc) ₄]4Ac ₂ O	Yellow solid	88°D	795	780.7	7.63	7.51	228.4	3.28
Cs ₂ [Ni(OAc) ₄]2Ac ₂ O	Yellow solid	98°D	752	764.7	7.55	7.67	215.0	3.46
(NH ₄) ₂ [Ni(OAc) ₄]4Ac ₂ O	Yellow solid	82°D	755	738.7	8.05	7.94	194.3	3.36
Tl ₂ Ni[(OAc) ₄]2Ac ₂ O	Yellow	86°D	930	907.4	6.54	6.46	218.6	3.44

D—Decompose

The carbonyl stretching mode present at 1740 cm^{-1} in pure acetic anhydride is slightly lowered to about 1726 cm^{-1} in these double acetates suggesting that the solvent molecules are not coordinated to the metal; rather they are held by the cation ion-dipole interaction which is in accordance with the T. G. A. studies as the solvent molecules are lost at comparatively low temperature. Symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes of the acetate group have been employed for the structural elucidation⁵. The difference in the symmetric and asymmetric carboxy group in a compound where acetate group acts as bidentate bridging group is expected not to be grossly different from that observed for the acetate group in sodium acetate and both the stretching modes move to the higher regions⁶. As no bands are observed around $1600\text{--}1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$, it rules out the possibility of bridging acetate group⁷ present in these compounds. Since the difference in the symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes is reduced and both the bands move to the lower region, it indicates that the acetate group is acting as symmetric chelating group. Apart from these bands, the bands, though low in intensity are also present at their original position and the difference in the symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes of the carboxy groups are not different from those found in $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\cdot\text{OAc}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ where acetate group acts as a monodentate ligand⁸ suggesting that in the compounds $\text{M}_2[\text{Co}(\text{OAc})_4]\cdot 4\text{Ac}_2\text{O}$ two of the acetate groups act as bidentate chelating agents and the rest of the acetate groups act as monodentate ligands and the central atom acquire a coordination number of six. A slight splitting of the asymmetric stretching mode in some of these compounds ($10\text{--}16\text{ cm}^{-1}$), is either due to the difference in the force constant or due to solid state interactions within the lattice. Metal-oxygen stretching mode expected to be in the range $400\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed at $\sim 420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of cobalt compounds and at $\sim 410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of nickel compounds. These modes are independent of the alkali metal used and these are observed at the same position as reported in literature^{9,10}. There is no experimental evidence to show that acetic anhydride molecules are directly attached to the transition metals; they are rather surrounding the cation and held in the crystal lattice by ion-dipole interaction.

The possible formation of these double acetates may be visualised as :

A possible structure where acetate group may act as bidentate chelating as well monodentate ligand may be postulated as shown at the bottom of the left column.

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Study of the Chelate of Divalent Manganese with 2-Hydroxy-1, 4-Naphthoquinone (Lawson).

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SURVEY of literature reveals that 2-Hydroxy⁻¹, 4-Naphthoquinone (Lawson) has found its application in qualitative and quantitative estimations of various metals¹⁻⁴. Recently we have studied and established structures of chelates of lawson with various metals⁵. In the present communication the composition, nature of structure, stability constant and free energy of formation of Mn^{++} : Lawson chelate is reported.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Lawson (K. K. Laboratories N. C. Plains view, New York, A. R.) and manganese chloride (B. D. H. AnalaR) were prepared by dissolving the respective compounds in double distilled ethyl alcohol (absolute).

To isolate the complex, 200 ml of Lawson (alcoholic) solution (0.01M) was added slowly, to 200 ml manganese chloride (0.01M) with constant stirring. The solution was then warmed and allowed to stand overnight. The deep red coloured crystals were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried at $62^\circ\text{--}67^\circ$.

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